

MOTIVATIONS AMONG EXPERTS IN INTERNATIONALIZATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION: THE CASE OF THE CALCA NETWORK

MOTIVACIONES ENTRE EXPERTOS DE INTERNACIONALIZACIÓN DE EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR: EL CASO DE LA RED CALCA

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SUMMARY: 1. Introduction, 2. University Networks: a Platform for Collaboration among Experts, 3. The Role of Motivation in University's International Networks, 4. CALCA Network: a Community of Internationalization Experts and Managers, 5. Methodology, 6. Results, 7. Conclusions, 8. References

ABSTRACT

Collaboration between academic peers and university managers has different characteristics and motivations, some are personal and others institutional, especially among internationalization professionals. The construction of networks and communities can be supported in a prospective and relevant way by knowing the factors that determine good collaborative practices among internationalization experts. This qualitative exploratory-descriptive study analyzes the motivations of a group of nine experts from Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Honduras, Mexico, and Peru participating in the Latin America-Caribbean-Germany Network (CALCA) formed by a group of the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) Alumni. These motivations were examined through a focus

RESUMEN

La colaboración entre pares académicos y gestores de las universidades tiene diversas características y motivaciones, algunas personales y otras institucionales, especialmente en aquellos profesionales de la internacionalización. Conocer los factores que determinan buenas prácticas colaborativas entre expertos de internacionalización apoyará la construcción de redes y comunidades de forma prospectiva y pertinente. Este estudio cualitativo de tipo exploratorio-descriptivo analiza las motivaciones de un grupo de nueve expertos de Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Honduras, México y Perú que participan en la Red Conecta América Latina-Caribe-Alemania (CALCA), constituida por ex becarios del Servicio Alemán de Intercambio Académico (DAAD).

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group identifying intrinsic and extrinsic motivations following the model of Stirling (2013) and Sansone & Morgan (1992). The results show that there is a greater weight in the intrinsic motivations that generate membership, synergy and collaboration linked to the personal and professional development of the participants of this network.

Estas motivaciones fueron indagadas a través de un grupo focal identificando motivaciones intrínsecas y extrínsecas siguiendo el modelo de Stirling (2013) y Sansone & Morgan (1992). Los resultados evidencian que existe un mayor peso en las motivaciones intrínsecas que generan pertenencia, sinergia y colaboración vinculadas al desarrollo personal y profesional de los participantes de dicha red.

KEYWORDS: Internationalization, motivation, network, higher education.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Internacionalización, motivación, red, educación superior.

1. INTRODUCTION

The process of cooperation between human beings is a phenomenon that goes back to the earliest stages of humanity and has meant, in general terms, a process to modulate self-interest and adapt to those of others around us, regardless of the factors that gestate and favor this interaction (Tomasello & Vaish, 2013; Fehr & Gintis, 2007).

In the current era, where the advent of globalization, the presence of an inexorable socioeconomic interconnection and the rise of information and communication technologies tailor human relations at different levels and dimensions, the analysis of the motivations that drive people to forge successful communities and social units becomes a highly relevant research area in different disciplines (Driskell et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2017; Fehr & Schurtenberger, 2018).

Within the field of education, the importance of seeking mutual interests with other people and institutions to build joint learnings through unity is especially related to cooperation and social aggregation (Kitchen et al., 2019). In particular, in the higher education context, actions such as linkage, extension and internationalization represent the vehicles through which individuals pass within the framework of increasingly global formal and informal relations (Knight & De Wit, 2018).

The internationalization of higher education as a natural process of academic cooperation is envisaged as a strategy that favors the incorporation of an international and intercultural dimension in institutions (Leask, 2015) by generating agreements and workspaces that reduce cultural, disciplinary and even personal barriers among university actors seeking similar objectives, therefore it

is extremely significant to analyze the socio-professional phenomena that occur when in the framework of this university internationalization, academics and managers converge on collaborative projects that aim to build networks to strengthen teaching, research and other functions such as culture dissemination or social engagement (Seeber et al., 2020; de Wit & Deca, 2020).

Based on this foundation, this work consists of three parts that aim to analyze the series of motivations and interests that a group of members of the Latin America Connect Network - Caribbean - Germany network show to belong and keep-on performing academic collaboration actions around internationalization of higher education. The first part addresses the series of conceptual and theoretical elements related academic cooperation, networking, motivation in university contexts and the sense of belonging to an academic community. The second part explains the methodology applied for this study: the design of a focus group, the selection of participants and the data analysis model. The last part describes the analysis of the results and the conclusions on the relationship between dimensions from a hermeneutic - interpretative paradigm.

2. UNIVERSITY NETWORKS: A PLATFORM FOR COLLABORATION AMONG EXPERTS

Academic collaboration has for at least two centuries, played a fundamental role in the advancement of knowledge and in people training processes at any level (Geuna, 1998). Through collaboration among

educational institutions, academics can share resources, experiences, technology and knowledge that not only strengthen their own institutions, but also develop new and innovative approaches that benefit society at large (Sharma & Kaushik, 2022; Wang et al., 2019).

Collaboration can manifest itself in various forms and contexts. Especially international academic cooperation represents a fertile ground for the creation of a global network of subjects and objects of knowledge, where the interconnection between institutions through mobility projects, joint scientific production and collaborative classroom or virtual teaching, promotes the expansion of the knowledge frontier, an increase in intercultural understanding, the diversification of students' vision and the construction of a global or intercultural citizenship (Trede et al., 2013; Byram & Golubeva, 2020).

Collaborative action in universities is carried out through different channels that can be interlinked or mutually exclusive. It is customary to think that universities through their institutional mechanisms generate agreements that allow them to carry out cooperation and internationalization actions (Knight, 2008), however, parallel to this, a set of individual or collective relationships are created, so collaboration can materialize in an interpersonal manner that usually work better than those relations established under an institutional umbrella (Fleming et al., 2016).

These formal and informal relationships are driven by various objectives and interests,

so networks can be created between national and international peers from different disciplines; aimed at promoting teaching and joint research actions; involve collaboration in the field of management, such as accreditations, student exchange, training or funding (Nicolaou & Birley, 2003); or there may be university networks of teachers and/or managers that originate from membership of organisations, professional profiles or sole personal interests (Sharma & Kaushik 2022).

Collaboration in the field of research, for example, plays a key role in the advancement and development of science, not only by expanding the scope and complexity of research, but also favoring the development of more comprehensive solutions on an international scale (Hall et al., 2018). The dialogue and interaction between scientists from different areas stimulate creativity and generate a proper environment to the emergence of new ideas (Maxwell & Stone 2004).

As for the university management, networks of university professionals (managers, coordinators, advisers, etc.) are carried out mainly through agreements or contracts aimed to establish projects or programs that strengthen intercultural learning, internationalization and the exchange of resources (Knight & De Wit, 2018) which allows educational institutions to build a kind of "macro" university system, leading them to a new sense of competition, in which they strive to stand out from the rest but recognizing that without building alliances they would not reach new horizons in terms of innovation, quality and global relevance (Hernaus et al., 2019).

International academic networks are considered as natural scenario for university cooperation and to foster interinstitutional links between university actors, where good practices are shared, knowledge and technology are transferred, the training of managers and academics is promoted, projects are developed and the implementation of the intercultural dimension in each institution is assisted. It is therefore extremely important to analyse the motivations that lead participants of these networks to work, stay and engage in them, understanding that there may be institutional incentives and other individual interests that stimulate collaborative action in communities of experts at the international level.

3. THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN UNIVERSITY'S INTERNATIONAL NETWORKS

Motivation has been one of the most studied processes in psychology and behavioral sciences. Classic authors such as Maslow, Herzberg and McClelland have been pioneers in the analysis of motivation. It is a dynamic state (Soriano, 2001) that can be studied only through manifestations (Chauliz, 2004), such as behavioral expressions, physiological or through self-reports and descriptions of the person who manifests such expressions (Reeve, 2010). It is a process composed of multiple components, which according to González-Cabanach and collaborators (1996), no current theory explains and integrates these components fully. According to

Albo (2009), this situation is the biggest limitation facing research in this field.

Carsrud & Brännback (2011) state that the study of motivation is aimed at answering three questions: what is it that activates a person to initiate and sustain his behavior? What makes a person choose one behavior over another? And why do different people respond differently to the same motivational factor? Herron & Sapienza (1992) indicate that motivation occurs within the individual, it is a properly individual process. Therefore, it seems clear that if one does not know what initiates and enhances an action, it will be very difficult to understand and to promote such.

Over time motivation has been characterized and classified in different ways. Intrinsic motives refer to the personal interest in the task, such as the motivation of achievement, an impulse from within that leads to action. Extrinsic motivation refers to all those reasons and rewards that are external to the subject (Bonilla Ballesteros, 2011; Cabrera et al., 2022). In general, numerous studies focus on those motivations that work as external rewards to the subject, for example, economic compensations, performance awards, increase status, etc., often leaving aside those that are more intrinsic (Marulanda et al., 2014; Bonilla Ballesteros, 2011).

Although different authors who work on the subject talk about the different motives that lead a subject to act, we consider that it would be a novel contribution to explore them and analyze what the nature of them is, in order to define and group them. In this case, we will focus specifically on those

reasons that lead a person to integrate and sustain their behavior in an international network, specifically, the CALCA network. University professors and managers seem to work in the field of international cooperation from a variety of extrinsic and intrinsic motivations. Many teachers consider that working with international colleagues and students is personally and intellectually enriching as it allows them to obtain alternative perspectives that help improve their research and teaching activities (Li & Tu, 2016; Cao et al., 2014). The interest in developing international actions also seems to benefit the university professors' careers. Conducting studies and publishing with international colleagues can increase the visibility, number of citations and funding opportunities for researchers (Dusdal & Powell, 2021; Fox & Faver, 1984).

Based on the above, one of the starting points for the creation of international networks of professionals involved in the field of international education seems to be associated with the construction of spaces that contribute to negotiation and mutual intercultural understanding (Avery & Wihlborg, 2013), where a series of elements derived from the clash of values, culture and educational objectives, within the framework of a complexity of economic, socio-cultural, ethnic and organizational factors actually occur (Wihlborg & Robson, 2017). In the same sense, the motivation of university professionals to belong and participate in global networks of collaboration can be sustained by a diversity of factors that are much more due to the perspectives of "role" or group identity, where organizational interests converge (institutional objectives) but

also other intra-organizational interests that respond to additional characteristics such as leadership, professional growth, the creation of a greater network of contacts or training for the development of a practical project (Hudzik, 2016; Seeber et al., 2016).

4. CALCA NETWORK: A COMMUNITY OF INTERNATIONALIZATION EXPERTS AND MANAGERS

Conecta America Latina - Caribe - Alemania (CALCA) is the Latin America and the Caribbean alumni network of the DIES-MOI (Dialogue on Higher Education Innovative Strategies - Management of Internationalization) training course that has been sponsored by the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) and developed by Leibniz Universität Hannover since 2014, in collaboration with other counterpart universities from the global south.

CALCA was established in early 2021, when a group of the DIES- MOI Alumni decided to evolve a set of informal collaboration between them and build a learning community exclusively for DIES-MOI generations, which allow the group to expand their experience into new projects and ideas in the field of internationalization in higher education. Most of its members are associated to a Latin American Higher Education institution (HEI), but there are also members who are currently working as independent international education consultants. The network fosters knowledge transfer, building capacities and the development of joint projects in the field of internationalization of higher education. It brings together 49 higher education

experts from 13 Latin American and Caribbean countries. It includes teaching and non-teaching staff like managers, administrative personnel, and researchers. As of today, CALCA has three cooperation priorities: 1) training and innovation, 2) communication and networking and 3) research in internationalization management and practices. The network's international scope across Latin America allows it to boost the internationalization dimension in various academic collaboration ecosystems. The network's headquarters are in cyberspace, providing an opportunity to connect synergies, capacities, learning and communication resources that enable shared, integrated, and collaborative work among its members. The Network is self-directed, voluntary, and results-driven, with a foundation of shared responsibility and mutual support and collaboration.

The network's mission and approach preserve, as defined by its members, a special link and connection to Germany, where CALCA trainees have progressively turned into specialists in the management of internationalization. Furthermore, it is worth noting that Germany has always been one of the most important partners in the Global North for the Latin American area, where the development of new collaborations with an impact on curricula and scientific research are the focus.

The group has also carried out during its three years of existence seven on-line plenary encounters, out of which one was a CALCA Identity and Image Workshop; one online education experience exchange

between Chile, Bolivia, Guatemala and El Salvador, on November 18th, 2021; one face to face meeting with the Centro Universitario de Baviera para América Latina (BAYLAT), in Erlangen, Germany in April 2022 and one online BAYLAT & CALCA encounter in May, 2022.

The network has been present in two official DIES events between 2021 and 2022, the DAAD International Conference, November 2021 and the DIES International FORUM, October - November 2022. In 2023, the network organized with the aid of a DAAD grant for Alumni Events, the first face-to-face encounter of its members, where the community developed discussion and actions towards four major areas: a) capacity building; b) CALCA strategic planning; c) organizational new framing: a LATAM network of experts in internationalization; d) internal and external networking. These meetings not only boosted the strategic alignments of the network, but also represented the kick-off of the CALCA image & brand.

Given the nature and characteristics of this network, the growth and expansion that have showed over the past three years, for being an initiative “from” and “for” its members and, especially for being a collaboration platform of experts in the field of internationalization in higher education, it represents a potential research phenomenon in which motivations and interests for collaboration becomes the

center of the analysis for this qualitative study.

5. METHODOLOGY

With the aim of analyzing from a qualitative - interpretive approach the set of motivations that the members of the CALCA Network show to belong and remain in this collaboration platform, and then reflect on the intrinsic and extrinsic forces that sustain these incentives, a focus group meeting was held with nine active network members from Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Honduras, Mexico and Peru, with the aid of a set of triggering questions including different categories of analysis defined by two researchers who are currently part of the network.

The selection of the focus group technique for this study was made taking into account the advantages of its use in perception studies, since this approach allows a more open discussion between the researcher and the respondent, promotes the diversification of discourse through the analysis of conceptual meanings and the establishment of an atmosphere of co-responsibility in group reflection (Wilson, 1997), unlike certain limitations that traditional interviews sometimes offer for the type of information that is intended to be obtained (Guest et al., 2017).

The design of this guiding instrument for the focus group development was based on the characterization of authors such as Stirling (2013) and Sansone & Morgan (1992), as they refer to the need to analyze and study the motivation of people in the framework of organizations from intrinsic and extrinsic

causes, as noted above. On the other hand, based on the diverse perspectives of internationalization that are developed in the framework of academic collaboration to have significant and useful information for the study. The invitation was made to 10 different people, trying to ensure that the list of participants had balance in terms

Table 1. Levels of personal motivation

Personal	Professional	Institutional	Community
The different drivers, motivations and interests as CALCA member.	Competences (global, intercultural or international) that are built through networking activities.	Contribution to institutional plans, programs or projects related to internationalization.	Benefits to the CALCA community as a whole by developing collaborative activities.

Source: Author's own creation

(Knight, 2008; Wihlborg & Robson, 2017), personal, professional, institutional and community levels were defined (Table 1), which allowed establishing categories of analysis to interpret the set of motivations that are generated within the main study object of the present research.

The CALCA network has as of today (2024) a total of 21 members, so the research team aimed to invite at least 30% of that number, which accounted for seven people of country of origin, gender, and position (academics and managers). A total of nine experts confirmed their participation in the focus group, for which email invitations were sent to arrange a date and time for the session.

Table 2. Triggering questions on motivation

Personal	Professional	Institutional	Community
- What has been the main drive to join CALCA? - What interests you as a member of CALCA?	- Is CALCA a motivating network? - What actions or activities have been attractive for your work? - Has your motivation changed in these two years?	- Was it a personal challenge or an institutional interest? - Is your institution interested in your CALCA membership?	- Why collaborate with peers in this network? - Is the CALCA team a good collaborative exercise? - Don't you already have enough collaboration platforms?

Source: Author's own creation

nine members agreed to participate in the dynamic, which was carried out virtually through the Zoom platform, lasting 90 minutes and with the participation of a moderator and an observer. The above-mentioned guide to trigger questions is shown in Table 2, which was used as a basis along with other questions and statements that emerged during the meeting.

After the focus group exercise and with the series of information obtained in it, different activities were carried out to review the results: the constant comparative analysis, content categorization, keyword analysis and discourse analysis (Onwuegbuzie et al., 2009), from which transcripts and interpretations were made based on the table of dimensions previously described.

6. RESULTS

The information collected on focal group participants was organized according to each of the motivation levels that were established for the design of the guiding guide for the group meeting. A word/concept map was used to highlight constant mentions

and trends of assertions by respondents. Once the information in this map was organized, internal and external motivators were identified (Stirling, 2013; Sansone & Morgan, 1992) and textual quotes were rescued that exemplify in each case.

Regarding the membership of the CALCA Network, the moderator inquires whether such membership was based on a personal or institutional interest, inquiring about the main reason for joining the network. With greater recurrence and considering the intrinsic motivators, the participants seek in CALCA possibilities of collaboration, networking, synergy and co-creation of social and research projects. The arguments converge in considering that the network integrates experiences, academic-professional development and interdisciplinarity.

I really like working with the network colleagues, it is comfortable and respectful. It promotes a creative work horizontality that I value deeply and makes me grow as a human being. CALCA makes me feel very valuable. My motivation is clearly individual at this time, although it began with my

Graphic 1. Word cloud on focus group results

Source: Author's own creation with the aid of ATLAS.ti

participation in the MOI course, it was not anticipated at that time the creation of the network, the network was an emerging desire of our fellow-classmates who wanted embrace that challenge, situation that is quite influential to CALCA's sustainability (Argentina).

The main impulse to join CALCA is that I love everything related to internationalization [...] The course in Germany helped me realize many things. I have always had an international vision because I believe that the world is global, and we cannot live in a single culture. CALCA is an excuse to be aware of other Latin American realities, which seem so similar and yet are quite different (Ecuador).

The main motivation has been people. I take part in several initiatives during the pandemic, working groups initiatives, networks [...] CALCA has this magic and made things possible [...] the impulse has definitely been the people who make CALCA (Peru).

Some of the aspects that stand out in the contributions of the participants is that the communication is fluid and the perceived leadership in the network is horizontal, which feeds the companionship, the collaboration, and the networking. It is stated continuously that CALCA is a community.

[...] With companionship, let us say that communication is facilitated, we identify ourselves as part of that program [...] There is also a lot of horizontality, we respect the knowledge, the expertise of each one. There is no such thing as an authority or a hierarchy, it is simply our own way of organizing (Mexico 1).

For academic evaluation, my institution cares about my membership to a network [...] I get extra points institutionally (Chile).

CALCA is composed of a group of people who have different formations, experiences and common interests, is a strong pillar, support for personal development [...] as CALCA we have a lot of information, and we also know other institutions of our countries (Chile).

The way in which you are invited to belong to CALCA is by showing results, you see a collaborative work [...] that invites you to be part of it (Colombia).

It is a network in which participants come not only from International Relations offices, but from academic and other contexts, that makes it very interesting to be able to expand knowledge (Colombia).

I would say that it is something personal [...] I'm not currently working in a higher education institution, but it is the commitment to continue contributing, even outside these academic workspaces [...] For me internationalization is not only linked to position, is a commitment from wherever we are (Mexico 2).

It is super important to collaborate with network peers, to see what others do... other colleagues' experiences always help build and expand our vision, so I think this collaboration is very important for the development of the region (Ecuador).

Among the responses it is evident that this group regards itself as unique, an original network that integrates several generations of the DIES-MOI (Management of Internationalization) course of DAAD and that it integrates different disciplines and professional backgrounds.

CALCA is a motivating network, the group has shown beyond being part of a network, that there is an interest in motivating each other to grow even more. The fact of having considered me before graduating from the course as part of the Communication Team

has allowed me to contribute to a graphic consolidation of the network (Ecuador). CALCA is a platform where people share an interest in making a powerful, quality, inclusive, international education that will bring a change in the Latin America society [...] CALCA is a privileged space where, among friends, I can continue learning, I can help and being helped at the same time (Peru).

From the institutional point of view, CALCA is considered a platform for potential formal collaboration. The experts who participated in the focus group emphasized institutional recognition and the possibility of generating new synergies with other institutions. Having the support of the DAAD (German Academic Exchange Service) is another motivator. In addition, the participants perceived that CALCA impacts the International Relations Offices in their own institutions.

My institution does not require membership of a network, but it is indeed something that is valued, especially when we work on the Internationalization office [...] so for me the institutional issue is very important (Honduras).

For my institution there is no obligation, no pressure to be in this type of networks, the motivation is absolutely personal. The ability contribute to the activities that we propose, to the initiatives that we develop, from the teaching, research or administrative functions, I believe that working in this type of networks allows us to amplify the impact incorporating the internationalization component in our different educational activities (Bolivia).

It is attractive for my university that I will belong to a network [...] but it is not an obligation that you have to meet

membership indicators, but it is visible and presented as a very important aspect (Colombia).

It is more a personal challenge, the institutional interest is not very evident since now I am not an internationalization manager, however, I consider that all the personal challenge, somehow, involves institutional development or institutional interest (Ecuador)

To close the focus group, the moderator asks participants to think synthetically about two words or short phrases that describe what they are looking for in CALCA, and what activity is most interesting to them as members of the network.

I am looking to collaborate; it is the most interesting activity [...] I would like to develop joint projects (Caso Colombia).

I am looking for networking on internationalization issues, making concrete projects and strengthening this network, which I believe belongs to us. My activities of interest are linked to building a platform, a team to which I feel I belong (Honduras).

I am looking for global citizenship through initiatives, so that people get attached to proposals, and of course, international synergy, networking [...] I want through this network to achieve educational projects that have an impact on human development (Bolivia).

I'm looking to collaborate, the activity I like most is research (Chile).

I am looking for collaborations and the activity that I like the most is networking, meeting more people and making contacts, that is super important" (Mexico 1).

Co-creation, bonding and social impact (Mexico 2).

I seek to contribute psychology to the development of competencies for internationalization through activities

such as research and collaborative curricular learning (Argentina).

I am interested in helping in everything that is possible from my professional expertise (Graphic Design) (Ecuador).

What interests me the most as a member is the support that we can all have to share issues related to internationalization, initiatives, we are inviting each other to make projects, this is very valuable and powerful [...] The meeting in Mexico was very important, it was where we got closer and inspired (Peru).

Finally, it should be noted that regarding the future of the network as a community of experts and learning, the participants in the focus group agree that, even though there are considerable facilitators and obstacles of the CALCA Network in an international context, CALCA has a lot of potential to strengthen itself, it must face the challenge of gaining recognition and legitimacy. It also motivates participants to become a network that can share learning and contribute with other networks, expanding its mission. Another recurring motivator is funding, which leads to the active search for grants that guarantee the network's economic sustainability for the upcoming years' activities. Finally, participants agree that an area of opportunity is to increase the quantity and quality of scientific publications that CALCA can produce in different topics related to international education.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The creation of international networks in the field of higher education depends on both individual and institutional factors

that foster cooperation and joint work among academic peers and managers. In the field of internationalization of higher education, the people involved in these processes seem to be willing to collaborate voluntarily and desire to contribute to the actions and projects in this area, there are also motivations that encourage them to engage at the international level in order to detonate academic relations, build identities in groups of mutual interest and create synergies, which are not necessarily aligned with formal institutional indicators. The CALCA network shows upon this study a strong and expanding level of integration and collaboration, given by a series of circumstances that address the impetus of its members and their commitment to the field of internationalization, even when they no longer belong to areas dedicated to such processes.

The support of the network, according to the results of the focus group, is strongly supported by intrinsic factors, which are based mainly on a sense of belonging to a community, on the democratization of the objectives of the organization, enabling a learning space based on the experience and good practices of its members and, thanks to the fact that the network was created by the will of the people, with a certain adherence to the guidelines of their institutions, but more by the conviction of a contribution to the field of internationalization, which has provided them with professional growth.

It is also important to highlight that upon this study a set of good practices of cooperation and internationalization can be identified as a result of the CALCA network

creation, which demonstrates the relevance of building networks of experts in this field. An example of this is the joint research that has taken place among some members, the achievement of a funded project by the German government or the generation of a face-to-face network meeting, which is extremely difficult to achieve when there are no institutional incentives. Another important achievement is the will to give sustainability to the network through planning actions and programming of joint academic activities, which will undoubtedly strengthen the development of skills, share good practices of internationalization, and explore new collaborative peer actions.

These results contribute to future research aimed to analyzing extrinsic motivations or factors in international academic cooperation or in the formation of networks of experts, providing key elements for the creation of membership, permanence, and support of such networks in the framework of higher education.

It is also notable that internationalization is consolidated as a transversal development area present in different university processes, as the commitment and motivation to participate in the CALCA Network is evenly evident from academics, researchers, managers, and independent professionals.

8. REFERENCES

- Avery, H., and M. Wihlborg. 2013. "Teachers' Interpretation of Bildung in Practice: Examples From Higher Education in Sweden and Denmark." *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education* 5 (3): 1-20.
- Bonilla Ballesteros, Á. B. (2011). Hacia una comprensión de la mente y el comportamiento del emprendedor. *Panorama*, (9), 141-161.
- Byram, M., & Golubeva, I. (2020). Conceptualising intercultural (communicative) competence and intercultural citizenship. In *The Routledge handbook of language and intercultural communication* (pp. 70-85). Routledge.
- Cabrera, A. D. R., Alva, W. A. R., & Bracamonte, S. M. O. (2022). Motivación: Elemento necesario para el desarrollo psico-productivo. *Journal of Neuroscience and Public Health*, 2(2), 215-224.
- Cao, Y., Li, X., Jiang, A., & Bai, K. (2014). Motivators and Outcomes of Faculty Actions towards International Students: Under the Influence of Internationalization. *International journal of higher education*, 3(4), 49-63.
- Carsrud, A. y Brännback M. (2011). Entrepreneurial Motivations: What Do We Still Need to Know?. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 0(49), 9-26.
- Chauliz, M. (2004). *Psicología de la motivación: el proceso motivacional*. Universidad de Valencia.
- de Wit, H., & Deca, L. (2020). Internationalization of higher education, challenges and opportunities for the next decade. European higher education area: Challenges for a new decade, 3-11.
- Driskell, J. E., Salas, E., & Driskell, T. (2018). Foundations of teamwork and collaboration. *American Psychologist*, 73(4), 334.
- Dusdal, J., & Powell, J. J. (2021). Benefits, motivations, and challenges of international collaborative research: a sociology of science case study. *Science and Public Policy*, 48(2), 235-245.
- Fehr, E., & Gintis, H. (2007). *Human Motivation and Social Cooperation: Experimental and Analytical Foundations*. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 33(1), 43-64.
- Fehr, E., & Schurtenberger, I. (2018). Normative foundations of human cooperation. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 2(7), 458-468.
- Fleming, S. S., Goldman, A. W., Correlli, S. J., & Taylor, C. J. (2016). Settling in: The role of individual and departmental tactics in the development of new faculty networks. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 87(4), 544-572.
- Fox, M. F., & Faver, C. A. (1984). Independence and Cooperation in Research. *The Journal of Higher Education*, 55(3), 347-359.
- Geuna, A. (1998). The internationalisation of European universities: a return to medieval roots. *Minerva*, 253-270.
- Guest, G., Namey, E., Taylor, J., Eley, N., & McKenna, K. (2017). Comparing focus groups and individual interviews: findings from a randomized study.

- International Journal of Social Research Methodology, 20(6), 693-708.
- González Cabanach, R., Valle Arias, A., Núñez Pérez, J. C. y González García, J.A.(1996). Una aproximación teórica al concepto de metas académicas y su relación con la motivación escolar. *Psicothema*, 8(1).
- Hall, K. L., Vogel, A. L., Huang, G. C., Serrano, K. J., Rice, E. L., Tsakraklides, S. P., & Fiore, S. M. (2018). The science of team science: A review of the empirical evidence and research gaps on collaboration in science. *American psychologist*, 73(4), 532.
- Hernaus, T., Cerne, M., Connelly, C., Poloski Vokic, N., & Škerlavaj, M. (2019). Evasive knowledge hiding in academia: when competitive individuals are asked to collaborate. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(4), 597-618.
- Herron, L. y Sapienza, H. J. (1992). The entrepreneur and the initiation of new venture launch activities. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 17, 49-49.
- Hudzik, J. K. (2016). Drivers of and speculation over the future of higher education internationalization. In *Global and local internationalization* (pp. 21-30). Brill.
- Kitchen, J., Berry, M., & Russell, T. (2019). The power of collaboration. *Studying Teacher Education*, 15(2), 93-97.
- Knight, J. (2008). Higher education in turmoil: The changing world of internationalization (Vol. 13). Brill.
- Knight, J., & De Wit, H. (2018). Internationalization of higher education: Past and future. *International Higher Education*, (95), 2-4.
- Leask, B. (2015). A conceptual framework for internationalisation of the curriculum. *Internationalizing the Curriculum*, 26-40.
- Li, B., & Tu, Y. (2016). Motivations of faculty engagement in internationalization: A survey in China. *Higher Education*, 71, 81-96.
- Lin, J.-S., Lee, Y.-I., Jin, Y., & Gilbreath, B. (2017). Personality Traits, Motivations, and Emotional Consequences of Social Media Usage. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 20(10), 615-623.
- Marulanda Valencia, F. Á., Montoya Restrepo, I. A., & Vélez Restrepo, J. M. (2014). Teorías motivacionales en el estudio del emprendimiento. *Pensamiento & Gestión*, (36), 204-236.
- Maxwell, S., & Stone, D. (2004). Global knowledge networks and international development: bridges across boundaries. In *Global knowledge networks and international development* (pp. 1-17). Routledge.
- Nicolaou, N., & Birley, S. (2003). Academic networks in a trichotomous categorisation of university spinouts. *Journal of business venturing*, 18(3), 333-359.
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., Dickinson, W. B., Leech, N. L., & Zoran, A. G. (2009). A qualitative framework for collecting and analyzing data in focus group research. *International journal of qualitative methods*, 8(3), 1-21.

- Reeve, J. (2010). *Motivación y emoción*. McGraw-Hill.
- Sansone, C., & Morgan, C. (1992). Intrinsic motivation and education: Competence in context. *Motivation and emotion*, 16(3), 249-270.
- Soriano, M. M. (2001). La motivación, pilar básico de todo tipo de esfuerzo. *Proyecto social: Revista de Relaciones Laborales*, (9), 163-184.
- Seeber, M., Cattaneo, M., Huisman, J., & Paleari, S. (2016). Why do higher education institutions internationalize? An investigation of the multilevel determinants of internationalization rationales. *Higher education*, 72, 685-702.
- Seeber, M., Meoli, M., & Cattaneo, M. (2020). How do European higher education institutions internationalize?. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(1), 145-162.
- Sharma, D. K., & Kaushik, H. (2022). A Study of Role and Importance of Academic Collaborations/ Memorandum of Understanding in Higher Education Institutions. In *2022 10th International Conference on Reliability, Infocom Technologies and Optimization (Trends and Future Directions)* (pp. 1-8).
- Stirling, D. (2013). *Motivation in education*. *Aichi Universities English Education Research Journal*, 29(2013), 51-72.
- Tomasello, M., & Vaish, A. (2013). Origins of Human Cooperation and Morality. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 64(1), 231-255.
- Trede, F., Bowles, W., & Bridges, D. (2013). Developing intercultural competence and global citizenship through international experiences: Academics' perceptions. *Intercultural Education*, 24(5), 442-455.
- Wang, J., Zhang, R., Hao, J. X., & Chen, X. (2019). Motivation factors of knowledge collaboration in virtual communities of practice: a perspective from system dynamics. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(3), 466-488.
- Wihlborg, M., & Robson, S. (2017). Internationalisation of higher education: drivers, rationales, priorities, values and impacts. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 8(1), 8-18.
- Wilson, V. (1997). Focus Groups: a useful qualitative method for educational research? *British Educational Research Journal*, 23(2), 209-224.